

Holocene lithic traditions on the Middle Nile in light of new data from Letti,

Sudan

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Abstract

The research of Early Holocene sites in the Middle Nile region enabled the establishment of general trends in technological traditions, including the creation of stone tools, ceramic vessels and subsistence. Nevertheless, the task of ascribing the origins of subsequent Neolithic tradition to these earlier ones was a challenging endeavor. This in turn served to reinforce the prevailing theories concerning the external origins of pastoral communities. Recent research at the Letti Desert 2 site from the 8th millennium BCE has yielded a substantial collection of stone tools associated with alternately pivoting stamped pottery, as well as the earliest remains of domesticated cattle in this part of Africa. In contrast to the industry of groups referred to as regional Mesolithic, the use of quartz in this complex was sporadic. Despite the evident differences when compared with Neolithic funeral deposits, close parallels are observable in the raw material preferences and composite tool-making technology.

Key words: Early Holocene, Neolithic, sub-Saharan Africa, lithic tools manufacture, geometrics, standardization

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Introduction

Sites located in the Middle Nile region (between the Third and Fourth Nile Cataracts) that date from the Early Holocene (earlier than 8.2kya = c. 6200 BCE) have long been identified as settlements of hunting and gathering communities. There is a long tradition of research associating this form of adaptation with analogous finds to the north (Lower Nubia – Shiner, 1968a, 1968b) and to the south (sites around Khartoum – Arkell, 1949; Salvatori et al., 2014,

and near the Sixth Nile Cataract – Caneva & Zarattini, 1983; Marks & Abbas, 1991). However, thanks to a steadily growing database of radiocarbon-dated contexts, the functional and cultural differentiation of these sites has progressed substantially in recent years (Honegger & Williams, 2015; Usai, 2016; Varadzinová et al., 2022; Varadzinová et al., 2023). Importantly, the notion of an exclusively hunter-gatherer economy of these Early Holocene communities has been challenged. The new data from site Letti Desert 2 (LTD2), notably including cattle remains bearing characteristics indicative of the early stages of domestication (Osypinska et al., 2025; Osypiński et al., 2023), suggest a local origin for the regional pastoralists and, by extension, also their technological traditions. This raises the question of whether Early Holocene stone-tool industries from sites such as LTD2 can be shown to be the direct predecessors of industries known from Neolithic pastoral sites? This article discusses the LTD2 finds in the context of lithic assemblages known from the Early and Middle Holocene sites in the region, the aim being to emphasize their significance for the evolution of local stone-tool industries.

The earliest Early Holocene finds of interest for the current discussion are those from the vicinity of Debba, lying between the Third and Fourth Nile Cataracts (Marks et al., 1968). A local periodization developed by the Combined Prehistoric Expedition researchers, introduced at least three groups characterized by different ceramic and stone industries. The Karmakol Group, defined in reference to Arkell's findings, was distinguished by pottery decorated with an overall wavy-line pattern; it was said to correspond to Early Khartoum assemblages. The Tergis Group was thought to be slightly younger. Pottery vessels representing this group were decorated with only a series of double dashes below the rim (alternately pivoting stamp) and they were characteristically few in number. There was also a negligible proportion of quartz among the stone materials from which various artifacts were made. The youngest in this set, the Karat Group, said to correspond to the Late Khartoum Neolithic in the south and the early A-Group in the north, was characterized by pottery decorated with a zigzag ornament. Without archaeozoological analyses of animal bone remains, the few hypotheses concerning the subsistence of all three groups tended to transpose contemporary knowledge about the prehistory of the lower reaches of the Nile Valley (the part of the river in Egypt), according to which only the Karat group corresponded to pastoral communities.

The understanding of the complex chronology of settlement and technological traditions in the early Holocene was significantly advanced by extended Swiss research in the Kerma region near the Third Cataract (Chaix & Honegger, 2014; Honegger, 2014; Jakob & Honegger, 2023).

The exploration of the el-Barga, Wadi el-Arab and Boucharia sites revealed unusually long-lasting settlements, enabling the analysis of artifact assemblages with precise absolute chronology from cut features (both habitation and burial sites) and stratified depositional levels with chronological resolutions of just several hundred years, dated to between 8300 and 5400 cal. BCE. In the words of the researchers, “These are not phases of occupation but an artificial division which makes it possible to organise the archaeological remains into groups and to follow their evolution over time” (Jakob & Honegger, 2023, p. 140). It has therefore been possible to identify the technological characteristics of the various phases relating to both pottery ornamentation and the composition of the lithic tool assemblages. While no specific “leading types” could be identified for the individual phases, clear trends emerged in the popularity of particular types of ornamental pottery and stone tools. The issue of cattle domestication was also important in this research. Despite initial presumptions that cattle remains were present in the earliest phases (Chaix, 2011; Honegger, 2007), it is now accepted that the earliest evidence of domestic cattle is from Phase V, around 6000 –5500, notably, a burial dated 6000/5800 cal BCE (Chaix & Honegger, 2014).

Enter now the LTD2 site, which is located on the desert fringes of the Letti Basin, 30 km north of Debba and 140 km south of Kerma. The deposits found there appear to be narrowly dated to just a few hundred years, with radiocarbon dates falling in the 8th millennium BCE. The pottery from the main assemblage features a characteristic alternately pivoting stamp decoration identical to that found on Tergis/el-Barga II ceramics. The uniformity of the ceramic workshop (88% of the sherds were of this type), coupled with the narrow dating of the site, provided the excavators with the rationale for treating the stratified layers as an undisturbed Early Holocene settlement. This was in contrast to sites in the Third Cataract region, where researchers had to contend with the effects of long-term/multi-phase occupation.

Context: the Site and Research Methodology

The LTD2 site was discovered in 2022 (Osypiński et al., 2022). Two trenches were excavated: LTD2/A (10 × 5 m) and LTD2/B (10 × 10 m) (Figure 1; Osypiński et al., 2023). The material discussed here mainly originates from the 0.5 m of accumulated deposits in trench LTD2/A, which also included cut features, such as pits, containing fragmented querns, lithics, pottery and animal remains (Figure 2). Radiocarbon dating of the ostrich eggshell fragments, which were frequently found in both layers and features, suggests that the 8th millennium BCE was the most likely timeframe for this period of occupation (Osypiński et al., 2022: Table 2). Only two samples yielded a younger date (the turn of the 7th and 6th millennia BCE), but these two

came from an analysis of cattle teeth (both dentin and enamel) based on carbonate fractions and, since none of these was burned, the dates could reflect secondary processes (recrystallization) occurring long after the death of the organism (pers. comm. T. Goslar).

The human bone remains from the trench surface (LTD2/A Locus 2) have been identified as burials that have been eroded by deflation. The radiocarbon dates for these remains cluster around the middle of the 5th millennium BCE (Osypiński et al., 2023, table 3), which is consistent with our current understanding of Neolithic settlement in the region. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the current surface layer (comprising Loci 1 and 2) contains remains of Early Holocene occupation mixed with later accumulations (e.g. eroded burials) and should be treated separately. Loci 3 to 5 are interpreted as undisturbed, Early Holocene layers and features, whereas Locus 6, composed of rock debris in a silt matrix that constituted the substrate in Early Holocene times, contained only trace quantities of Early Holocene finds. The stone artifact assemblage from this last horizon was dominated by much older finds from the Middle Stone Age (MSA). Distinguishing between the two groups of lithic products was straightforward in view of the state of preservation of the artifacts and the parameters of individual pieces (Osypiński et al., 2023, fig. 12). In summary, the three stratigraphic horizons are as follows: (1) a surface layer (comprising Loci 1 and 2, marked in yellow in Figure 2), extending down to a depth of 10 cm, containing eroded Early Holocene remains as well as Neolithic burials; (2) a homogeneous/undisturbed Early Holocene horizon (comprising Loci 3–5, marked in brownish shades in Figure 2), with a thickness of half a meter, including cut features; and (3) the deepest-lying layer, which constituted the substrate in the Early Holocene (comprising Locus 6, marked in gray in Figure 2).

Figure 1. Letti Desert 2 (LTD2) site and its environs. Compilation of a DEM image and orthophotomap showing the location of explored areas (LTD2/A and LTD2/B) and the full extent of early Holocene remains (red dashed line)

Figure 2. A: section through the stratigraphy of the explored loci, as traced on the southern wall of trench LTD2/A; B: raw materials in each exploration unit grouped according to stratigraphic horizons: yellow – current surface; brown – homogenous Early Holocene deposits (upper and lower); gray – Early Holocene background level

The lithic production technology was determined based on a macroscopic analysis of the raw material, chaîne opératoire analysis and a typological study of retouched tools. This also enabled the frequency of given types of formal tools in the assemblage to be established. Particular attention was paid to the size and morphology of geometric backed tools, which were the main component of the stone industry. The results were interpreted in light of regional blank production and tool typology, with the data from LTD2/A being compared to the published results of research on assemblages from other Early Holocene sites as well as some later, Neolithic deposits in the Middle Nile Valley.

Lithic Assemblage

The lithic assemblage from the archaeological exploration of trench LTD2/A counted 11,330 artifacts (Table 1). Broken down by layer, this amounted to 1880 (about 17%) lithics from Locus 6, which contained almost exclusively Pleistocene (MSA) products; 6553 artifacts (58%) from Loci 3–5, representing Early Holocene occupation from the 8th millennium BCE; and the rest, 2897 (25%) items, from the modern ground surface (Loci 1–2), comprising some Early Holocene artifacts mixed with lithics of possibly later date.

Table 1. General structure of the lithic assemblage from LTD2A. In each cell, the successive numbers, separated by backslashes, represent the data for the following loci in this order: 1–2, 3–5 and 6

Technological category	Quartz	Agate	Chert	Ferruginous sandstone	Quartzite sandstone	Petrified wood	
Cores	0/10/7	3/5/1	51/199/40	0/5/6	0/0/0	0/0/0	327
Cortical butt flake	15/31/11	14/20/2	145/333/85	5/5/0	0/0/1	0/0/0	667
Plain butt flake	16/43/21	19/37/0	350/1337/295	36/100/23	2/1/0	0/1/1	2282
Prepared butt flake	0/13/20	8/3/1	98/403/237	21/25/11	0/0/0	0/0/1	841
Edge/point butt flake	0/36/17	17/25/0	170/631/135	4/15/2	2/0/0	0/0/0	1054
Chips/chunks	37/18/7	64/35/3	801/375/74	22/2/4	5/0/1	5/2/0	1455
Blade plain butt	0/4/0	1/0/0	14/125/14	0/0/0	0/0/0	0/1/0	159
Flake fragments	0/81/52	34/61/0	651/1958/698	25/111/11	2/0/0	0/4/0	3688
Tools	1/8/4	9/15/0	247/441/82	1/13/8	0/1/0	0/1/1	832
Rejuvenation elements	0/0/0	1/1/0	1/18/3	0/0/0	0/0/0	0/0/1	25
Total	69/244/139	170/202/7	2528/5838/1663	114/276/65	11/3/2	5/9/4	11330

Focusing just on the Early Holocene horizon (Loci 3–5), the presumed multiple recurrence of occupation episodes at this site during the 8th millennium BCE does nothing to undermine the excavators' view that the lithic assemblage, like the pottery, reflects a single technological tradition. This justifies treating this assemblage as a singular whole.

Strongly preferred as a raw material in this assemblage were the local cryptocrystalline rocks: chert/flint and agate (Figure 2), all accessible as pebbles in riverine deposits. The 4.1% share of agate in the undisturbed Early Holocene assemblage (compared to 0.4% in the Pleistocene set and 6% in the surface deposits) can be considered as an indication of such preference. In contrast, noncryptocrystalline quartz accounted for only 2% of the Early Holocene collection, compared to 7.4% in the MSA assemblage from Locus 6 (and 2.5% in the surface deposits).

Quartz was clearly not a preferred raw material for the stone tool makers and users at the LTD2 site. The same can be said of various kinds of sandstone. Products made of this raw material appear in all horizons at the site, but this particular kind of stone was evidently not the material of choice for making formal tools in the Holocene. It could, however, constitute waste from the production and use of large equipment, such as hammers, grinding stones and querns.

One should note the heavy fragmentation (dominance of the fragmentary flake category in Table 1) and secondary overheating of the lithics (there is no evidence of intentional thermal treatment to improve stone-processing properties). This indicates intensive use of the area (trampling, intended and unintended transportation of small objects) and of the stone artifacts themselves.

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Figure 3. Selected cores, tools and production waste from trench LTD2/A. Scale bar=2 cm (2x1 cm). Items r and s come from surface loci (1–2); the rest are from undisturbed loci 3–5

Of the more than 200 cores made of chert and agate (not including the discoidal and Levallois cores from the Pleistocene horizon), none were found to show the signs of initial processing only. Clearly, the collection is characterized by a high degree of processing. Most of the cores from LTD2/A are small in size (the remaining flaking surface is about 30 mm long) and sometimes feature a change in the direction/reorientation in the latest single-platform reduction episodes (Figure 3(a,b)). Direct percussion is the only processing method noted, accompanied by abrasion of the platform/flaking surface edge and platform rejuvenation. Crested blades (occasionally used as a tool semi-product, Figure 3(c)) constitute evidence of blade reduction methods. Blades were the predominant form of tool blank (as can be seen in Figure 4), sometimes measuring almost 60 mm in length, though generally much shorter at around 40 mm, with widths ranging from 5 to 20 mm and thickness of up to 5 mm. Much larger blanks, approximately 10 mm thick, were used to make scraping and notched/denticulated tools. However, it is unclear whether massive flakes with natural cortical surfaces were the outcome of other production processes or simply waste from processing blade cores. Similarly, single bipolar pieces in the collection could be interpreted as the result of the reuse of waste products from blade production (e.g. the rejuvenation tablet, Figure 3(d)) rather than as forms intended to be bipolar from the outset.

Figure 4. Size (mm) of geometric tools from the Early Holocene horizon (Loci 3–5) in trench LTD2/A

Geometric tools are the predominant formal tool category at the site (Table 2). These pieces were made from regular blades, although less regular blanks are also in evidence. The extraordinary gracility of some of the tools (Figure 3(g–n), for example) and the presence of a

few waste products of characteristic shape (six examples, among others Figure 3(r–u)) suggest the application of a microburin technique.

However, tools that are definitely not made using this technique are much more common and the waste products mentioned above could have been produced accidentally. The geometrics from LTD2 were classified as follows: truncations (retouched side either oblique or transverse to the long axis of the blank), trapezes (two retouched edges either oblique or transverse), backed blades (straight side retouched lengthwise), crescents/lunates (arched side retouched lengthwise), triangles (side retouched lengthwise, divided into two parts joining at an angle).

Table 2. LTD2/A: formal tools made of chert and agate (numbers in brackets)

Formal type	Modern surface (Loci 1–2)	Early-Holocene sediments (Loci 3–5)	Early-Holocene background level (Locus 6)
Truncation	18 = 9.1%	43 = 10.8%	2 = 3.1%
Backed blade	12 (+4) = 8.1%	32 (+3) = 8.8%	3 = 4.6%
Crescent	59 (+8) = 34.1%	147 (+8) = 39%	1 = 1.5%
Triangle	6 = 3%	3 = 0.8%	0
Trapeze	1 = 0.5%	0	0
Perforator	23 = 11.7%	18 = 4.5%	1 = 1.5%
Borer	8 = 4.1%	1 = 0.3%	0
Burin	1 = 0.5%	0	0
Endscraper	3 = 1.5%	25 = 6.3%	0
Scraper	28 (+1) = 14.8%	27 = 6.8%	17 = 26.1%
Sidescraper	0	15 = 3.8%	3 = 4.6%
Denticulated tool	7 = 3.5%	22 = 5.5%	12 = 18.5%
Notched tool	18 = 9.1%	38 (+1) = 9.8%	14 = 21.5%
Bifacial foliate	0	5 = 1.3%	7 = 10.8%
Mousterian point	0	6 = 1.5%	2 = 3.1%
Levallois flake/point	0	3 = 0.8%	3 = 4.6%
	197 = 100%	397 = 100%	65 = 100%

Figure 5. Selected tools from trench LTD2/A. Scale bar=2cm (2x1cm). Items e, h and q come from surface loci (1–2); the rest are from undisturbed loci 3–5

Figure 6. Size of geometric tools found on the surface (Locus 1) in trench LTD2/A

The size range of Early Holocene tools within given typological categories was determined through an analysis of complete tool measurements (Figure 4). The smallest artifacts in the assemblage were 11–12 mm long (two crescents from undisturbed Early Holocene contexts and two more from the ground surface layer, all made of chert: Figure 3(e,f)). However, the majority of the crescents/lunates ($N = 99$) fall within the 15–26 mm length range (median 20 mm) and the 4–11 mm width range (median 7 mm). These tools were made of chert and agate. All the complete triangles also fall within this range (Figure 3(o–q)). The evident concentration of tool sizes indicates some kind of standard that determined their production, most likely imposed by the size of the bone or wooden shafts or frames assuming the geometrics were cutting inserts. It also suggests a way of use necessitating frequent replacement of damaged or missing composite inserts. The second size category for geometric tools is characterized by much larger dimensions which are less clustered in terms of size. These tools, made exclusively of chert, are more than 26 mm long and up to 23 mm wide (Figure 5(b–d,f–g)). Tool types include crescents as well as truncations and backed blades. The use of these tools was clearly not as standardized as in the case of the smaller inserts; they could have been inserted into different frames or shafts either individually or in more arbitrary configurations. The truncations and backed blades, in particular, could have been used as arrowheads given their weight. The sole trapeze in the LTD2 assemblage (also assumed to be a transverse arrowhead)—found on the surface – falls in this size category, too (Figure 5(e)). There are evidently no tools longer than 30 mm found in the surface layers (Figure 6), which leads to the assumption that, beginning in

The only example of a burin, made from a partly cortical flake, comes from the surface. It is a truncated burin type (Figure 5 (q)), traditionally used for grooving hard organic materials such as bone. However, the piece from LTD2 showed no microwear traces.

Scrapers from trench LTD2/A with semi-abrupt retouch are represented by regular endscrapers (28 pieces, only three of these from the ground surface, Figure 5(k–m)) and the much more ad hoc scrapers (56 pieces, 29 of these from the surface). A further 17 tools of this type were found in Locus 6. This suggests that the production/use of scrapers (considered as a formal type) is not chrono-distinctive. There is, however, an evident predominance of large scrapers in the oldest loci, presumably reflecting the availability of such flakes (as tool blanks) during the MSA occupation of the site. In later Holocene loci, scrapers were made from smaller blanks (Figure 8). The wide size range in this category is also noteworthy. Pieces larger than 30 mm in both length and width could be older (MSA) items redeposited in Holocene strata.

Figure 8. Size range of complete endscrapers (circles) and scrapers (squares) from the three stratigraphic horizons in trench LTD2/A

Twelve of the 28 scrapers were made from flakes with no cortical surfaces (for endscrapers, it was 38 out of 73). Therefore, it cannot be concluded that flakes from the early processing stages

(that is, preserving some cortical surfaces) were a clearly preferred form of blank for making scrapers.

Similar difficulties arise when determining the chronology of notched tools commonly identified as ad hoc instruments for processing plant fibers and animal tissues based on their typology (Figure 5(o–p)). These tools were found in the early Holocene deposits, as well as on the surface and as a major component of the MSA tool assemblage (traseological analyses of this tool category from Affad have suggested that they were used for cutting soft animal tissues; Pyżewicz,2025).

The assemblage from the Early Holocene horizon (Loci 3–5) at the LTD2/A site also yielded sidescrapers that were flat-retouched along one edge, bifacial and unifacial tools (lanceolate and Mousterian points) as well as Levallois products. However, the presence of products of this kind in these contexts is most likely more or less accidental, as they were part of the late Pleistocene substrate. A discussion of these tools is beyond the scope of the current study.

Contextualizing the Lithic Industry from LTD2/A

To understand the importance of this clearly uniform technological tradition at the LTD2/A site, it must be considered alongside published data on Early and Middle Holocene assemblages in the Middle Nile Valley. The possibility that it may be the earliest evidence of stone tool production among the proto-pastoralists of the Nile Valley further augments its significance.

“Tergis industry”

Published studies of stone tool collections representing the so-called “Tergis industry” refer to the finds as ‘microlithic’, but do not specify the actual size of the blanks and formal tools. Drawings illustrate a variety of final cores with flaking surfaces measuring no more than 40 mm in length or width (Hays 1971b, fig. 3). The largest of the illustrated ones are around 70 mm (e.g. Hays 1971b, fig. 4s). Most blade tools were produced from blanks corresponding in size to blades roughly 40 mm long and 10 mm wide (e.g. Hays 1971b, fig. 4f, 4l).

The raw materials recorded at the four Tergis Group sites included Nile pebbles, local chert and agate, as well as the significantly less common quartz pebbles, and materials in the “other” category, such as quartzite, petrified wood and ferruginous sandstone. It can be assumed that the CPE team did not have any difficulty in distinguishing between “Nile pebbles” and “local

chert”, even though the grounds for making this distinction are not specified in the publication. Perhaps, in this case, the chert was of the pale beige variety with clearly visible lime cortex, justifying its classification as a local stone. This type of raw material was commonly used at Early Holocene as well as Pleistocene sites around Affad and Argi, and in Multaga (Osypiński 2025b; Osypiński et al. 2022). In summary, Tergis Group assemblages are dominated by products made of cryptocrystalline rock, whereas quartz and the ‘other’ category of stone seldom exceeds 3% in the formal tools category and 20% in production waste. This clearly distinguishes them from the Karmakol Group, where quartz was much more commonly used (sometimes accounting for up to 50% of the assemblage). The proportion of quartz in the LTD2/A assemblage was significantly lower (Figure 9).

Turning to the cores, the dominant form in the Tergis Group was either a single-platform core for blades with a flat platform (Single *Lisse*) or else formed by faceting (Single Facet). The LTD2/A assemblage is similar in nature.

The list of formal tools from Tergis covers 21 items (Hays 1971b, Table 5). Top on the list are geometric tools (lunates, trapezes, triangles), which rarely exceed a combined total of 12%. A few microburins are noted even though this kind of processing is not thought to have been common. The group of geometrics, which should also include truncations and backed pieces, constitutes between 15.8% and 43.2% of the total count of retouched items. No large forms, exceeding 30 mm in length, can be seen in the illustrated material; the sole exception is a robust backed piece (Hays 1971b, fig.4h).

The Tergis perforators recorded in the published drawings are clearly mostly made from flakes (Hays 1971b, figs.6h-k), which correspond to the forms found in the surface layer in trench LTD2/A.

Scrapers are numerous in the Tergis assemblages: standard scrapers, large core scrapers and sidescrapers (which are actually more like endscrapers) and raclettes. The LTD2/A assemblage did not contain any large scrapers, which are instead associated with the secondary use of Pleistocene forms. However, tools of this kind, especially the notched variety, were present at the Early Holocene site of Multaga 3 (see below) and in other assemblages characterized by a high proportion of quartz.

Denticulate and notched tools in Tergis Group assemblages always fall within a similar range of between 19.8% and 25.3%, which is higher than in Early Holocene contexts from LTD2/A (corresponding to a Pleistocene reality more than anything else).

Burins were limited to individual tools, which again corresponds to the evidence from LTD2/A.

In conclusion, Tergis Group assemblages differ from the Early Holocene collection from LTD2/A in that they have a much smaller proportion of larger blades (>30 mm) used for producing geometrics, different preferences regarding the blanks used for perforators and scrapers, and a higher proportion of denticulated and notched forms. Assuming that the local chert identified by the CPE team at Tergis is the same light-colored stone found at Multaga and Argi, this would also differentiate Tergis from LTD2/A. However, the exceptionally low proportion of quartz in the raw material composition is shared by both.

Figure 9. Location of Early Holocene assemblages in the Middle Nile Valley: red diamonds – assemblages from the 9th–8th millennium BCE, including pottery with alternately pivoting stamp decoration; orange diamonds – other Early Holocene assemblages with wavy line/dotted wavy line pottery; navy blue diamonds – Neolithic assemblages from the 5th millennium BCE. Pie charts for each site show the share of various raw materials: blue – quartz; orange – chert/flint; red – agate; yellow – local chert; white – other.

El-Barga, Wadi el-Arab, Boucharia I Group

The next group to be considered are the assemblages from sites on the Third Nile Cataract. In terms of both time and pottery style, the finds collected from the fill of a habitat at the site of el-Barga (Honegger 2004) are the nearest parallel for LTD2/A assemblage. The el-Barga

assemblage has been radiocarbon-dated to between 7500 and 7100 cal BCE. The collection includes stone tools, pottery decorated with alternately pivoting stamp, querns and skeletal remains of wild mammals and fish. Information about the lithic assemblage, which has not been published in detail (similarly as the collection from Wadi el-Arab), is limited to a study of microliths (Honegger 2008) and, indirectly, from a general study of Early Holocene cultural transformations in the region of upper Nubia (Jakob and Honegger 2017). Complementary data comes from an assemblage from another Early Holocene site, Boucharia I (Honegger and Jakob 2022), the chronology of which, however, corresponds to earlier settlement episodes in the region (8200–7800 BCE).

The el-Barga assemblage was dominated by products made from cryptocrystalline chert pebbles. The same can be said of Boucharia I, where tools made of quartz constituted just 1.7% of the collection. The correlates of all of the production stages were present in both assemblages: cortical flakes, splinters, preparation flakes, cores with one or two striking platforms, discoidal cores and predetermined tools.

Of the 119 formal tools found at el-Barga, 21% were small geometrics (16–27 mm long and 5–8 mm wide), 10% were large geometrics (over 30 mm long and 9 mm wide), 13% were backed pieces, and 6% were perforators (without specifying the dimensions, although a close examination of the drawings suggests that both backed pieces and perforators were produced from blanks corresponding to the large segments category). Scrapers, which made up 8% of the formal tools, appear to have been made most often of cortical flakes roughly 30 mm long and at least 30 mm wide. The remaining 41% encompass other forms, such as denticulated and notched tools. A similar percentage distribution of the individual tool categories is evident in the Boucharia I assemblage: of the 39 tools, 21 were small segments, two were large ones, five were backed pieces, one was a truncation, another a triangle, four were flake denticulates, one was a scraper made from a partly cortical flake and four were *ad hoc* tools. Looking at the percentages, it can be seen that 77% of the formal tool set consisted of geometrics produced from microlithic blade blanks (or at the very least, a gracile form with elongated proportions). No perforators or burins were recorded.

The extensive and differentiated damage observed on the small segments from el-Barga merits attention. It ranges from simple breaks to lipped fractures, step fractures and sometimes bipolar and burin removals. According to Honegger (2008), this suggests that the small segments were

being used as arrow- and spearhead points, while the large ones, which featured only simple breaks, served as inserts on harvesting knives.

The data from LTD2/A and the results of a study of the combined el-Barga and Boucharia assemblages coincide, representing a microlithic stone blade industry based on local cryptocrystalline raw resources. In both cases, small segments made from blade blanks were the dominant tool category. The larger inserts demonstrate a much greater diversity in terms of both form and size (Figure 10). The remaining tool categories (scrapers, denticulates, and notched tools) used partly cortical blanks, which were probably waste products from the initial core reduction phases. The microburin technique has not been recorded in the Third Nile Cataract region (pers. comm. B. Jakob).

Other Early-Holocene (Mesolithic) Industries

Paradoxically, there is little reliable data on other Nubian sites from before 8.2kya (the abrupt cooling event that brought the early phase of the Holocene to an end). A shared characteristic is a predilection for wavy-line and dotted-wavy-line decoration on pottery (Gatto 2006), which occurred in conjunction with an economy based on the exploitation of aquatic/riverine biomes. A specific regional variety of this pottery from the Middle Nile, which is tempered with thick chaff, has been radiocarbon-dated, the results showing a clustering of dates around 7200–6500 cal BCE (AFD121 and AFD128) and 6450–6100 cal BCE (AFD125 and MTG3). However, the homogeneity of lithic collections from these sites should be concerned with cautions because most of them come from surface deposits at extensively eroded sites (also see: Hays 1971a). Even so, the large percentage of stone artifacts made of quartz (almost half of the total assemblage) clearly distinguishes these sets from those in trench LTD2/A. Such extensive use of quartz appears to be justified by the shape of small natural quartz pebbles. When flakes are struck from simple cores with platforms that are not pre-formed, these flakes can be used as inserts without any retouch. Examples of the use of such quartz flakes come from Neolithic graves at Kadero (Kobusiewicz 1996). Although quartz artifacts displaying single-platform processing and retouching are sometimes found, they are definitely in the minority (e.g., at Multaga 3, only 0.3% of the retouched tools were made of quartz – Osypiński 2025b; similar percentages were recorded in assemblages from the Fourth Cataract – Osypiński 2010; and Karmakol sites revealed a range between 0.6 and 6.7% – Hays 1971a).

Crucially, the non-homogeneous nature of assemblages from these sites makes it impossible in principle to determine the stone industry represented by most of the artifacts made of cryptocrystalline raw materials. The presence of tool forms (mainly backed types) that are similar to the tools found in trench LTD2/A at sites dating to the 7th and 6th millennia BCE presents an interpretative challenge. These tool forms are practically indistinguishable unless there is evidence in the form of refittings or the finds originate from homogeneous contexts (for instance, the fill of cut features). For the sake of an example, the several thousand products from the MTG3 site, combined with refittings of a few representative blocks, have revealed the contemporaneous use of at least three separate methods of obtaining blanks for producing different tools (Osypiński 2025b). The identified methods are: the single-platform blade-oriented method using large-size blocks of chert; the flake and chunk method using raw stone of the same size; and the microlithic blade production using small pebbles. These methods could reflect three different technological traditions, or indicate that three different product categories were in demand at the same time.

Neolithic (Middle Holocene) Lithic Production

Later flint knapping in the region also merits examination. However, the homogeneity of stone tool assemblages from Neolithic sites in the region is questionable, because the sites are usually exposed on the surface (deflated), the preserved remains mixed with earlier (Early Holocene) occupation. In this situation, funerary assemblages take on exceptional value. The deposit from burial LTD2/B/B.7 is certainly of this type (Osypiński et al. 2023), as are also some funerary assemblages from the R12 cemetery (Usai 2008) and a deposit of stone tools from Multaga 2 (MTG2/D17: Osypiński 2025a).

The LTD2/B/B.7 assemblage, which was radiocarbon-dated to 4174–4036 cal BCE (Poz-164658), contained three small inserts of chert and agate, as well as a few irregular flakes and an initial core of chert. These size of these three inserts is highly consistent (Figure 10). Two of these lack the apices, but it is difficult to ascertain whether this is due to use or, more likely, to fitting into a gap in the working edge of a composite tool. These tools were hardly made for the grave; they must have reflected everyday occupations of those involved.

Similar tool assemblages have been found in over a dozen Neolithic burials at the R12 cemetery in the northern part of the Dongola Reach. The cemetery has been radiocarbon-dated to between 4920–4670 cal BCE and 4540–4320 cal BCE (Salvatori 2008). A third of these burials (52 out

of 154) contained chipped stone artifacts (Usai 2008, Table 4.10), with the percentage share differing from a single tool to 87 pieces in a single burial. Of greatest significance in this case are the sets of inserts, mostly small and very small lunates made of cryptocrystalline rock (agate, flint, chalcedony, “exotic flint/Kordofan flint”). Burial sets ranged from one to a dozen pieces (maximum 11 lunates + 11 backed pieces), but no functional contexts were ever recognized (arrangements that suggest function). These tools, produced from flakes and microlithic blades in equal measure, correspond in size to most of the small tools found in trench LTD2/A. Very small segments, shorter than 10 mm, are also present. Some of the tools interred with the deceased were damaged (broken tips: Usai 2008, Fig. 4.11: 2, 19, 27, 31), indicating their utilitarian nature (despite the stated lack of any use-wear traces on the lithics). In addition to lunates, tools deposited in the R12 burials included backed pieces, perforators, scrapers and notches/denticulates, this apart from cores and flakes.

The most notable assemblage was the one discovered by the SFDAS in 2002 in the Multaga area (Geus and Lecoite 2003). Among the numerous Neolithic burials, manifested on the surface by clusters of small pebbles, was a deposit, MTG2/D17, containing a variety of utilitarian objects, but no human bones. Included in it were, among others, polished axes, bone tools (among them three composite knife frames) and over 100 stone artifacts. An *Aspatharia* shell from the fill above the deposit was radiocarbon-dated to 4726–4538 cal BCE (Poz-5455: 5790±40bp).

Two observations are of particular interest here. Firstly, the size range of the crescents (Figure 10) is very similar to that of the small tools from LTD2 and el-Barga. Secondly, the set is utilitarian in nature: similar to LTD2/B/B.7 and R12, the tools from MTG2 bear numerous traces of damage to the apices (assumed impact caused by fitting into a frame) and 23% of them show evidence of (presumably unintentional) overheating. Whirl-shaped perforators/borers made exclusively from blades appeared alongside the lunates in the deposit. Cryptocrystalline chert and agate were the only kinds of stone used, and all the blanks, whether flakes or blades, were prepared in the microlithic tradition. Butts are preserved in many cases, and they are strictly single-negative examples.

In summary, the Neolithic assemblages from the Middle Nile resemble those from LTD2/A in that there is little interest in quartz as a raw material for tool production. Toolmakers focused on making microlithic inserts for composite tools, such as knives with straight cutting edge,

mounted in a bone frame. In terms of size, Neolithic geometrics closely resemble the modular size of the so-called ‘small tools’ from el-Barga and the LTD2/A trench. The segments from Neolithic deposits do not represent the same large variety, which corresponds to the exclusively microlithic nature of the blanks used by the industry.

The bone frames for composite knives in the Neolithic funerary assemblages (Kadruka 1: Reinold 1994; R12: Salvatori, Usai 2008, Plate 7.2; MTG2/D17: Osypiński 2025a) are particularly significant because they would have accounted for the majority of chert inserts produced. Replacing the damaged components of these tools required a high degree of standardization in terms of their size and shape, although this did not rule out the secondary use of certain components. This explains the high proportion of damaged or burnt tools of this kind found in Neolithic funerary deposits. However, we can only speculate that Early Holocene tools of a similar size and shape were used in the same way. Use-wear analyses of the Early Holocene tools, from LTD2/A as well as Multaga and other assemblages, have not yielded conclusive evidence. The sheen-like layer on the surface of all of the artifacts resembles the effect of long-time processing of animal skin, but its presence on almost all the surfaces suggests a non-anthropogenic origin (pers. comm. K. Pyżewicz).

Figure 10. Dimensions of lunates from the two Early Holocene settlement sites: LTD2/A and el-Barga (after: Honegger 2008, fig. 15) and the 5th-millennium BCE assemblages

Conclusions

A detailed study of the stone-tools and pottery at the LTD2/A site reveals a close resemblance of its technological tradition to that represented by the inventory from a habitat excavated at el-Barga. The latter site has also yielded animal bone remains, which were initially identified as cattle, but this has since been refuted. Furthermore, pottery featuring alternately pivoting stamp decoration, which constitutes the majority of the LTD2/A material, has also been found at other sites in the Third Cataract region. Tergis Group assemblages revealed minor differences, as well as components representing different, as yet undetermined, phases/episodes of settlement. Nevertheless, the distribution of this type of pottery (alternately pivoting stamped) in the Middle Nile Valley suggests that it was widely used by early Holocene communities in the region, while the modest numbers of identified vessels indicates periodic or even occasional settlement. This is quite different from the extensive, and presumably long-lasting, so-called Mesolithic/Karmakol settlements. Another distinctive feature of the Mesolithic/Karmakol settlements, one that differentiates them from the communities inhabiting LTD2, was their preference for quartz when making stone tools (Figure 9). Later (Neolithic) industries in the region apparently did not share this preference. Given the poor state of preservation of Early Holocene settlement relics on the Middle Nile, which seriously impacts any observation of non-Mesolithic (non-Karmakol) components, LTD2 in the Letti Desert has turned out to be the first site where such research can be conducted (Table 3).

Table 3. Summary of technological features of the Middle Nile sites/industries in relation to sites in the Kerma region (Honegger, Jakob 2022). Gray arrows indicate shifts in periodisation suggested by LTD2 materials.

Phase (dating), in Kerma region	Karmakol	Tergis	Karat	Multaga 3	LTD2/A
V: 6000–5400 cal BCE First burnished pottery, rocker stamp decoration, bifacial lithic tools, large lunates			Thin, burnished sherds, “wolf-tooth” design; flake- based industries, small lunates		
IV: 6500–6000 cal BCE Rocker stamp decorated pottery, lunates, backed points, borers	Wavy Line and Dotted Wavy Line pottery, lunates made of blades, borers, scrapers; large share of quartz	 Alt. piv. stamp decoration, small backed tools, flake perforators and scrapers, single burins; “local chert”		Chaff- tempered pottery, small and big lunates, blade-made borers, scrapers; large share of quartz; light-beige chert (mined?)	
III: 7300–6500 cal BCE Herring-bone pattern, dotted wavy line pottery, lunates, backed points, truncations					
II: 7900–7300 cal BCE Alternately pivoting stamp decorated pottery, irregular retouched blades					
I: 8300–7900 cal BCE Return technique decoration on pottery, burins, scrapers, triangles/ trapezes, irregular retouched blades					

Direct links between pastoralism and stone-tool production components (by implication, elements of weapons or tools) are difficult to establish, regardless of the epoch. The querns and grinding stones found in trench LTD2/A are consistent with the extraordinarily composite characteristic of the local stone industry and the presence of vessel pottery. The processing of cereals (both wild and domesticated) must have been reflected in the harvesting *instrumentarium*, even if the use of geometric inserts for this purpose has not been confirmed until now for lack of traseological evidence. Geometric points could well have been used also as arrowheads and daggers/spearheads (a tradition reaching back into the Pleistocene, not only on the Nile). However, contrary to Honegger’s (2008) suggestion, the smaller inserts show much greater uniformity of size (a trend continued in the Neolithic), which would have made them suitable for fitting into wooden or bone frames. In turn, the wide variety of types and sizes among tools longer than 26 mm makes their apparent use as arrow/spearheads more likely. The

same can be said, however, of the “Mesolithic” inventories; therefore, it is pointless to search for correlates of a different adaptive (pastoral) strategy among the stone products.

In spite of this, the stone assemblage from LTD2 sheds light on the origins of the Neolithic, blade-oriented industry, which relied on cryptocrystalline stone and was focused on composite inserts. Current knowledge of stone industries in sub-Saharan Africa at the turn of the Pleistocene and in the beginning of the Holocene suggests the existence of analogous technocomplexes/traditions (e.g., Arkinian, Ballanian), although these have only been identified in the Western Desert and Lower Nubia (Schild, Chmielewska and Więckowska 1968; Vermeersch 1992; Schild and Wendorf 2010; Vermeersch 2020). Regions situated even further south or on the banks of the great lakes (such as Mega-Chad), are completely unknown, while they could well have served as potential refuges during the last glaciation (LGM). However, the absence of quartz from the palette of raw materials used to make stone tools suggests that the technological tradition discussed here was different to that of the contemporary Mesolithic/Karmakol/Early Khartoum-related units.

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Author contributions

P.O. conceived and designed the project, and interpreted the data. M.O. analysed the bone sample. M.Ch. analysed pottery assemblage. P.W. provided maps and plans. All the authors were members of the team exploring the Letti sites and contributed to the manuscript draft. All authors approve of its submission to this journal.

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